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Poetry in contemporary children's and youth literature: reflections on characteristics and trends

The third edition of the academic journal of Linguistics and Literature, **Revista Letras Raras (RLR)**, from the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande) is out. It is launched one more issue this year 2021 in which professors, students, and young and experienced researchers contribute to the composition of this special issue **Poetry in contemporary children's and youth literature: reflections on characteristics and trends**, that is organised by the professors and renowned researchers in the field of children's poetry: Eliane Aparecida Galvão Ribeiro Ferreira, from the São Paulo State University, Campus Assis (UNESP); Rosana Rodrigues da Silva, from the University of the State of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), and Sara Reis da Silva from the University of Minho (Portugal).

This third edition of 2021 has the collaboration of authors-researchers who helped in the construction of this special issue and the considerations from other fields of literature and from discourse analysis. The authors of the papers, translations, interviews and literary productions are from different origins: among papers and interviews, in addition to the universities already mentioned, there are authors from Brazilian universities as Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Federal Institution of Education, Science and Technology, Sertão Pernambuco (IFPE), Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), University of Pernambuco (UPE), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), State University of Maringá (UEM), Federal University of Ouro Preto (UFOP), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Western Pará (UFOPA) and Federal University of Northern Tocantins (UFNT). The authors from universities abroad are from University of Glasgow (United Kingdom), University of the Azores (Azores-Portugal) and University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain), as well as the aforementioned University of Minho (Portugal).

The essay that is present in this issue is from the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC). Among the translations, the authors are from: Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), State University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UEMS) and Federal University of Santa Maria (UFSM). Considering the creative texts, the authors are from the Catholic University of Mozambique (Mozambique), Federal

University of Ceará (UFC), Federal University of Cariri (UFCA), State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ) and Federal University of Bahia (UFBA).

Dear reader, we invite you to read the papers, the translations, the interviews and all the other texts that constitute this special issue. Share them with your colleagues and with your students. This gesture of sharing knowledge reiterates that doing science in the field of Linguistics and Literature is, today, in Brazil, an act of resistance. Thus, together, even if physically distant, we resist for the praxis of freedom, as Paulo Freire taught us, to whom, in this edition launched in the beginning of spring, we pay tribute for his centenary.

You can also access the texts of this issue by pointing the camera of your mobile phone to the QR Code of the journal and choosing the text you would like to read. With best wishes for happier days, we wish you a great reading!

Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz
Marco Antônio Margarido Costa
Maria Angélica de Oliveira

Editors of **Revista Letras Raras**: an Academic Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

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Translated by Walter Vieira Barros